

Preliminary observations on the incidence of some rice diseases in relation to planting dates and growth stages

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Knowledge of changes in the disease situation due to shifts in environmental conditions, and of the occurrence of diseases at particular stages of crop growth permits the selection of the proper screening season and the testing of breeding populations against particular diseases. We undertook a field experiment with different planting dates and observed the attendant disease situations at the Rice Research Station, Chinsurah. TN1 and Padma were used as test materials. Transplanting began in the first week of December 1973 and

continued at monthly intervals until October 1974.

Rice tungro, bacterial blight, and sheath rot were observed at three stages of growth: 1) early tillering, 2) maximum tillering, 3) 15 days after flowering. The preliminary results indicated that the incidence of the diseases differed in relation to planting dates as well as to stages of crop growth (see figure). The period of susceptibility to tungro was from September to October; to bacterial blight, from February to August; and to sheath rot, from December to May. While the crop is susceptible to tungro at the early and maximum tillering stages, and to bacterial blight and sheath rot at the flowering stage, the period of susceptibility to any disease may vary, depending on the factors that favor its development.

Incidence of three diseases of rice in relation to planting dates and stage of plant growth, Chinsurah, India, 1973-74.

Pest management and control

INSECTS

The rice brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* Stal in Karnataka, India

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In recent years the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* Stal (BPH) has been reported in epidemic form in several countries of Southeast Asia. India reports its appearance as a serious pest in fairly large tracts of rice in various places. However, the literature has had no report of its occurrence as a pest in Karnataka state.

In May 1975, BPH was noticed in a form so severe as to cause hopperburn patches in one rice field near Mandya. Later during kharif (July–October) 1975, the pest was reported from Mandya, Mysore, Shimoga, Chitradurga, Chickmagalur, Bangalore, Bellary, Tumkur, Raichur, and North Kanara districts in Karnataka. Thus, the pest appeared to be widespread in Karnataka, though in small patches in each place. Some rice varieties that have been attacked are Jaya, IR20, MR 301, IET 2295, and S 701. BPH infestation seems likely to become severe in all rice-growing areas of Karnataka.

Occurrence of rice mealy bug in Kerala

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The rice mealy bug *Ripersia oryzae* Green, considered a minor pest of paddy, has recently become important in parts of Quilon and Alleppey Districts in Kerala. Infestation was severe in the first crop paddy sown in April–May in unirrigated and upland fields. Lack of monsoon rains aggravated the infestation.